

The Current Situation, Problems and Countermeasures of Legal Regulation on the Coordinated Development of Express Industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei

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ABSTRACT

Based on the theory and practice of Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei integration strategy and regional industrial synergy legal regulation, this paper focuses on the analysis of the coordinated legal regulation of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei regional express delivery industry.

First of all, after reviewing the development status of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei express industry, understand the overall development of the industry. To pave the way for the specific study of the legal regulation of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei express industry. From the perspective of norms, the theoretical basis of collaborative development is analyzed to lay the foundation for subsequent discussions. Secondly, it studies and analyzes the basic status quo and problems of the coordinated legal regulation of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei express industry, analyzes the relevant laws and regulations, government regulations, etc., and points out the outstanding problems in the current legal regulation, mainly: Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei Regional administrative barriers, legislation still needs to be improved, local development imbalances and demands are not uniform, and the industrial structure layout needs to be optimized. The conclusions of the above problems are drawn and the ideas for subsequent legal regulation recommendations are provided.

The regional industrial synergy is improved in legislation, judiciary and law enforcement. Based on the specific status quo and problems that hinder the coordinated development of the express delivery industry in the three places, feasible suggestions and suggestions are put forward based on the development of regional industrial integration in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. Establish a sound regional coordination legal system, improve the internal management of express delivery enterprises, and strengthen the self-discipline mechanism of the express delivery industry to ensure the realization of the respective interests of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and to enable the development of the express delivery service industry in the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region.

KEYWORDS: *Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei integration Industrial synergy ; Legal regulation*

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Research purpose

The coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei is a major decision made by the Party Central Committee and the State Council with Comrade Xi Jinping as the general secretary. In recent years, the economic level of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei has been improving continuously, which is a strategic place to promote the economic development of northern China. Under the influence of the rapid development of Internet economy and the trend of informatization, the express industry is gradually developing under the leadership of e-commerce industry. However, the legal system of China's express industry is not mature. The contradiction between the existing laws and regulations and the increasingly innovative mode of coordinated development of express industry reflects that the legislation of express industry is relatively backward. In order to make the existing legal system meet the growth mode of express

industry, the government should improve the laws and regulations of express industry as soon as possible and establish a systematic legal system of express industry.

The coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry is not only to meet the development needs of the three regions, but also to better implement the Beijing Tianjin Hebei integration strategy. The cooperation among regions promotes the integration of resources among the three regions and strengthens the core power of regional development. Of course, the coordinated development of regional express industry must be guaranteed by legal system. Under the background of regional coordinated and integrated development, it is of great positive significance to discuss the legal regulation of the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry for the common

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and rapid development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry.

B. Research significance

1. Theoretical significance

The research on the legal regulation of the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei is conducive to the theoretical research on the legalization of the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and to the deepening of the legal construction and academic significance of the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. This topic discusses the market regulation and legal system from the perspective of mechanism, the legal regulation mechanism and path improvement of express industry; analyzes the new development concept, practice and legal basis from the perspective of norms; studies this topic with the concept of balanced coordination. The establishment of perfect laws and regulations can effectively safeguard the common interests of the region; the operation of express industry in accordance with relevant laws and regulations can promote the friendly cooperation and development of express industry among regions.

2. Practical significance

The coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei industry is in line with the general trend of international urban development. It can play a radiation role and play a gathering function in the Bohai economic circle. At the same time, it can also provide good opportunities for the further development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. The express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei not only meets people's daily needs, but also accelerates the influx of a large number of social capital into the express industry. The express industry and e-commerce industry are developing together. On the other hand, Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry is also actively entering the international market, accelerating the development of international express business. Through the study of its legal regulations, it is conducive to put forward more scientific countermeasures and suggestions for the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry, promote the establishment of tripartite cooperation mechanism, and implement more comprehensive and effective legal supervision measures for the government to express enterprises in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region, and finally Promote the express industry to make greater contribution to Beijing Tianjin Hebei region.

C. Research status at home and abroad

1. Domestic research status

At present, the research on this topic in the academic circle of our country is not mature, at the initial stage, no scholars have directly put forward relevant opinions on this topic. Most of the experts and scholars studied the legislative guarantee of the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei industry and the development strategy of express service industry.

Li Jie (2018) pointed out that the coordinated legislation of Beijing Tianjin Hebei region needs to be deepened and improved, and should be supported and led by the legal system at the central and local levels. Efforts should be made to strengthen the top-level design, formulate special laws to ensure that the coordinated development strategy of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei continues to advance in depth, build a

mechanism to guarantee the coordinated legislation and introduce the system of public participation, so as to ensure the scientificity and effectiveness of the legislation. [1]

Zhang Youmei (2019) points out the problems that need to be solved urgently by studying the current legal governance path of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. Regional coordinated development must be stabilized in the way of legal governance, strengthen cooperation and exchanges among the three regions, standardize regional governance organizations, establish the concept of integration of the rule of law, and strengthen the mechanism of coordinated settlement of regional conflicts. [2]

Gao Weiwei (2017) pointed out that the development of e-commerce requires more and more express delivery. The local government should strengthen the guidance, strengthen the cooperative law enforcement of all relevant management departments, jointly carry out a comprehensive inspection on the operation and service of express service enterprises, severely punish the illegal behaviors of express enterprises, and do a good job in identifying the professional qualifications of employees. At the same time, express enterprises should also strengthen internal management, establish a sound management mechanism to promote the healthy development of express enterprises. [3]

Wang chunye (2018) first analyzed the legal barriers and causes of regional development, mainly including three factors: the interest demand of the three regions is not unified; the coordination measures of the legislative system have not been followed up; the content and implementation of local legal provisions are different. It emphasizes that the integration of legal system plays a key role in the coordinated development, and holds that only through cross examination of the original local legislation and on the basis of full consultation, can a good legal environment be built for the regional integration of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei by innovating the way of legislative cooperation. [4]

Wu Tian (2018) believes that it is urgent to complete the perfect legal construction to serve the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. At present, the regional cooperation is relatively loose, and various disputes caused by the lack of perfect legal system and communication mechanism are difficult to solve. In order to promote the balanced development of the region, we should establish the corresponding benefit compensation mechanism. [5]

2. Research status abroad

Jun Juan Zhong, Jian Wang (2010) pointed out that the postal law and its supporting law, measures for the administration of express business license, were promulgated and implemented in October 2009, which greatly shocked the express industry. In order to promote the reorganization of express industry and optimize the industrial structure, the absolute concentration method was used to investigate the concentration of express industry in China. According to the calculation results, the influence of market concentration factors is analyzed from the aspects of scale economy, entry barriers, product differentiation, policies and regulations. Finally, two ways to improve the industrial concentration are proposed. [20]

According to the research of Na Chen e goodarstvo, the western Balkan countries have jointly established a small market in the region, which is committed to improving regional cooperation, EU integration process and the development of the world market. The regional integration of the western Balkans is an important aspect of European integration. Deepening cooperation and trade among the western Balkan countries will bring economic and political benefits to the region by reducing trade barriers, increasing foreign investment and improving the business environment. In 1999, as the main body of cooperation in the western Balkans, the international community formulated the stability pact for South Eastern Europe, which was changed into a regional cooperation committee in 2008. In 2017, the European Union proposed the idea of the western Balkan economic zone as a tool for further integration of the region. This institution can play a role in coordinating and supporting the political, economic and institutional agenda in the western Balkans. [21]

The above domestic and foreign research data show that the coordinated development of express industry is the inevitable trend of regional economic development in the future. Only by establishing a good regional cooperation mechanism and improving the legal system of the coordinated development of express industry, can the integrated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei region be guaranteed. However, there is still a lack of research on the legal regulation of the coordinated development of express industry. Therefore, this paper will analyze the problems faced by the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry in view of the deficiencies of the above domestic and foreign research, combined with the actual development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry and existing laws and regulations, and lay the foundation for the coordinated development of regional express industry.

D. Research methods

1. Literature research method

Through the interpretation of existing laws and regulations and regulatory documents, such as the postal law of the people's Republic of China, express business operation guidelines and express market management measures, etc., through discussion and guidance with the tutor, determine the research direction and main content, collect and read a large amount of domestic and foreign literature, and at the same time, widely collect and regional express with the help of the Internet On the basis of literature, we can draw general conclusions, find new problems, find new ideas and put forward new ideas.

2. Comparative research method

This paper compares the development of express industry in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region and the current situation of legal regulation with the legal regulation and government policies of relevant economic regions at home and abroad, and puts forward scientific and instructive suggestions for the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region.

3. Investigation and research method

Through field research on relevant legislatures, government departments and express service enterprises, we can get a closer understanding of the current situation of the legal regulation of the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region.

E. Definition of relevant concepts

1. Coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei

The Political Bureau of the CPC Central Committee held a meeting on April 30, 2015 to review and approve the outline of Beijing Tianjin Hebei coordinated development plan. The coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei is a major decision and deployment made by the Party Central Committee and the State Council under the new historical conditions, and an important national strategy of China. The three regions of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei are regarded as a whole coordinated development. With the orderly deconstruction of Beijing's non capital functions, the solution of Beijing's "big city disease" as the core, the adjustment of urban structure and economic structure, the promotion of industrial transformation and upgrading, the promotion of public service co construction and sharing, the creation of a new modern capital economic circle, and the formation of a new situation of coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei with complementary advantages and win-win results. We should focus on strengthening top-level design, increasing the promotion of integrated development, breaking the thinking pattern of separating the three areas and developing each other, establishing a sound cooperation mechanism and developing together. Accelerate industrial docking and cooperation, and form a reasonable layout of industries among regions.

In order to promote the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, the State Council established a leading group and relevant offices to strengthen the top-level design and overall coordination of the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. Under the leadership of the Central Committee, Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei also set up the Beijing Tianjin Hebei coordinated development leading group, which is responsible for the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei. Relevant ministries and commissions also set up special leading groups, such as transportation integration leading group, tax work leading group, etc.

The coordinated development of industry is an important support to promote the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. In order to ensure the smooth development of the coordinated development of industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, the three regions of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei accelerated the removal of institutional barriers restricting the development of the three regions, and successively introduced and improved relevant institutional mechanisms in many aspects such as regional cooperation, industrial docking, ecological joint defense and joint control, so as to make regional advantages complementary and win-win system The degree system is gradually improved.

2. Express industry

Express delivery, also known as express or express delivery, is within the scope of express delivery, whether it is bulk goods or small goods including documents. Express industry refers to the logistics activities that express companies deliver documents or parcels from the sender to the receiver quickly and safely by means of roads, railways, air transport and shipping. The main links of express service include: receiving and sending, sorting, sealing and sending, transportation, delivery, inquiry and complaint. Complaints and compensation, etc.

3. Legal regulation

The so-called regulation refers to the government's regulations. As a specific institutional arrangement, regulation is "the government's management or restriction of economic behavior". It is the government's behavior of intervening in the activities of economic subjects (especially enterprises) under the market economy system, aiming at correcting and improving the internal problems of market mechanism. Legal Regulation refers to a kind of norm formulated or recognized by the state, which is ordered, allowed and prohibited by the authorized administrative organ for the behaviors or activities of citizens and market subjects. The object of legal regulation is usually behavior rather than system, which refers to the use of laws and regulations to restrict and restrict its behavior. The state regulates the subjects of economic activities by means of law, economy and administration.

II. Development status and legal regulation status of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei

With the rapid development of China's economy and the growing maturity of online shopping, the e-commerce industry is also growing, the types of online goods are more and more complete, the quality of goods and the security of transactions are constantly improving, more and more people choose the online shopping model, as a collaborative industry of e-commerce industry, the express industry also continues to maintain a high-speed and steady development Exhibition. In 2018, China's express business volume has accumulated 50.71 billion pieces, and the business revenue has accumulated 603.84 billion yuan. The industry has great development potential and gradually becomes a black horse in the development of national economy. Not only that, China's express industry business also ranks first in the global market scale.

A. Development status of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei

In the rapid development tide of the whole industry, the express delivery industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei also maintained a stable and rapid development, and the main business development was stable and orderly. According to the data in 2018, the total volume of express business in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region has completed 4525878000 pieces, realizing the business income of 59926.635 million yuan. Beijing Tianjin Hebei region accounts for about 8.9% of the National Express business. It can be seen that the business volume of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry is huge, and it plays an important role in the national express industry.

1. Development status of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry

With the rapid development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, the volume of express business and the revenue of express business show a steady upward trend. According to the data of the volume and revenue of express business in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei in 2018, there is a large gap between the three places' express business affected by the local economic development level factors. The volume and revenue of express business in Beijing are both ahead of those in Hebei and Tianjin.

The intelligent and technological level of express service has been deepened. With the rapid growth of express business

volume, express enterprises have invested in the application of modern information technology and intelligent equipment, such as Internet of things, big data, cloud computing, etc., and built a number of automatic sub inspection centers, greatly improving the efficiency of commodity storage and sorting, and realizing the intelligent level of express service. For example, Jingdong Logistics enterprise built the first cold chain automatic sorting center before the June 18, 2018 Shopping Festival. The sorting center serves the whole North China region and introduces intelligent automation equipment from commodity storage, sorting, transportation in logistics center and other express logistics links, which greatly improves the efficiency and safety of express logistics.

At the same time, the quality and efficiency of express delivery service of all enterprises have also been significantly improved, the coverage of express service has been expanding, and the number of urban and rural distribution outlets has increased. By March 2019, the number of express delivery outlets in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei has exceeded 20000, and the punctuality and satisfaction of express delivery have been improved. With the development of express industry, more and more express service enterprises begin to attach importance to the concept of "Green Express", and apply the concept of green environmental protection to all aspects of express, such as: environmental protection packaging, packaging recycling, new energy vehicles, intelligent technology equipment are used in daily express service. Beijing Tianjin Hebei Express has also further expanded its international business and stepped forward to the international development. Some express service enterprises have set up outlets overseas, built overseas warehouses, overseas special lines and other ways to go to the international market, and carried out the express service from Beijing Tianjin Hebei express distribution center to some countries. These measures can not only enable express service enterprises to rapidly expand new business, but also further expand their influence in the international express market.

2. Analysis on the trend of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry

The coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei provides a good development environment for the transformation and upgrading of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. The coordinated development strategy of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei not only effectively relieves the non capital functions of Beijing, but also optimizes the regional industrial structure. This strategy effectively promotes the regional industry docking cooperation and complementary advantages, and promotes the transformation and upgrading of express service with extensive development. The promotion of Beijing Tianjin Hebei transportation integration strongly supports the flow integration and layout optimization of express delivery resources in the region. The application of modern information technology and intelligent equipment in express industry promotes the innovation and development of regional express industry. At the same time, the proportion of service industry is gradually increasing. The upgrading of industrial structure and consumption structure in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei will stimulate the demand of express delivery market.

B. Constraints on coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry

1. Unbalanced development and inconsistent demands in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei

As there is a big gap between the economic level and comprehensive strength of the three regions, the development of express industry is unbalanced. As the capital of our country, Beijing has strong economic strength and many unique resources. Tianjin, as the economic center around Bohai Sea, also has certain economic foundation and development potential. Although Hebei Province is a large industrial province, the economic strength gap between Beijing and Tianjin is still significant. Therefore, the legal regulation of the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei should start from the overall interests of the region, take into account the three areas, and promote the balanced development of regional express industry.

As the political, economic and cultural center of our country, Beijing carries too many non capital functions, which leads to the serious "big city disease". The core of the coordinated development strategy of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei is to orderly relieve Beijing's non capital functions and manage Beijing's big city disease. As the undertaking place of Beijing's moving out industry, Hebei aims to undertake more pillar industries and optimize production. The industrial layout promotes the industrial upgrading and transfer, but in the current situation, it can not produce a strong pulling effect on Hebei Province.

2. The industrial structure layout of Beijing Tianjin Hebei region needs to be optimized

There is also a big gap in the industrial structure of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. The industrial cooperation among the three regions still stays in the circulation of resource elements. Compared with Beijing and Tianjin, Hebei's industrial structure is at a lower level, so it needs to strengthen the deep and extensive industrial cooperation with Beijing and Tianjin. In addition, the number of cross regional industrial clusters in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei is small, and the convergence and extension of the industrial chain are not smooth, which undoubtedly hinders the docking, cooperation and optimization transfer of the three industries. The coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei needs scientific and balanced industrial layout and intelligent innovation drive to form industrial synergy advantages and form a win-win situation based on the long-term interests of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. Instead of only considering the treatment of urban diseases in the capital and the relocation of non capital industries, the interest demands and future development plans of surrounding areas are not considered.

C. The current situation of legal regulation on the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei

1. Legislative status

There are three main laws, regulations and departmental rules involved in China's express industry. One law is the postal law of the people's Republic of China. In Chapter 6, articles 51 to 60, it makes relevant provisions on the operation license of express business, the legal matters of industry associations and express delivery personnel. In chapter 5, Article 47, it also stipulates the compensation for express delivery, So that the express industry to carry out a

comprehensive rectification. The regulations of express market management measures and express business operation license management measures have made more detailed and perfect provisions on specific express business license, specific business and legal responsibility to strengthen the management of express market. On May 1, 2018, the Interim Regulations on express delivery promulgated and implemented by the State Council standardized and guaranteed the operation, use and supervision of express business. In order to further promote the implementation of the Interim Regulations on express delivery in the three regions, Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei also carried out in-depth learning and implementation related activities, such as the establishment of a leading group for publicity and implementation, the implementation of the work plan, the active docking with local governments, and the active guidance of mainstream media, so as to promote the practical implementation of the regulations in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei.

2. Law enforcement status

At present, under the unified leadership of the State Postal Administration, Beijing post administration, Tianjin post administration and Hebei post administration respectively supervise and manage the express delivery market in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and implement the national laws and regulations, policies and service standards on postal industry management. The postal administration departments of each region shall respectively carry out law enforcement inspection on the express delivery enterprises within their respective jurisdiction, and strictly investigate and deal with the illegal enterprises according to law. During the "two sessions" in 2019, Beijing post administration strengthened joint law enforcement, and jointly organized a joint inspection team composed of the Municipal Public Security Bureau and the municipal National Security Bureau to conduct law enforcement inspection on a number of distribution centers of express enterprises, and to conduct full coverage inspection on the distribution centers of major express enterprises in the city. However, at present, the scope of joint law enforcement is limited to other law enforcement departments within the jurisdiction, and no unified law enforcement cooperation department of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry has been established, forming a perfect law enforcement cooperation mechanism.

III. Basic principles and significance of coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry

A. Basic principles of coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry

1. Principle of legal system unification

The coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei should adhere to the principle of legal unity. The regional legal coordination is an important part of maintaining the legal unity of our country. In the coordinated development of express industry, Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei should first abide by the provisions of the Constitution and the upper law. In addition, coordinated legislation should be carried out among the three regions to maintain the legal unity.

2. Market leading principle

The coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei should adhere to the principle of market

leading, take the market demand as the guide, give full play to the main role of enterprises in the express market, accelerate the transformation of government functions, give full play to the role in legislation, planning, policy, law enforcement and justice, deepen the simplification of administration and decentralization, combination of release and management, optimize services, stimulate the vitality and creativity of market main body, and release The policy dividend of express industry development promotes fair competition in express market.

3. Principle of overall consideration

The coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei should adhere to the principle of overall consideration, integrate the current development situation of the three regions, take into account the development interests of the three regions, and coordinate the interest subjects of the three regions. The coordinated development of several land industries in Beijing and Tianjin not only requires the coordination of the interests of the three regions, but also requires the consideration of the development of express delivery in the three cities and rural areas. On the basis of in-depth research, it is necessary to promote the balanced development of large, medium and small express delivery enterprises, optimize the industrial structure and industrial layout, make the express service fully cover the three areas, and form a new pattern of coordinated development of express delivery.

B. Significance of improving the legal regulation of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry coordination

1. Provide guarantee for the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei industries

In the process of the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry, there will inevitably be various obstacles, which must be guaranteed by a strong legal system. Improving the legal regulation of the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry can not only coordinate the interests of the three parties, promote the innovation and cooperation of the three industries, but also provide an important institutional guarantee for the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei industry, and promote the regional politics, economy and culture of Beijing Tianjin Hebei , the cornerstone of social and ecological health development.

2. Conducive to the full implementation of the rule of law

Under the premise of ruling the country by law, the lack of legal system is difficult to guarantee the development of regional integration. To improve the legal regulation of the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, to further promote the administration of various administrative departments in accordance with the law, and to accelerate the construction of legal post, is conducive to the full implementation of the rule of law at the legislative, judicial and law enforcement levels. While Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei improve the legal regulation of the coordinated development of express industry, they should consciously stay in the great process of comprehensively governing the country according to law, adhere to the principle that there are laws to be followed, laws to be obeyed, laws to be enforced, and violations to be prosecuted.

3. Provide demonstration for the improvement of the law of the coordinated development of regional industries in China

At present, the process of regional integration in China is speeding up, and the mode of coordinated development of regional industries is an important strategy for China's economic development. Under this trend, a set of perfect legal regulations on the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry can provide demonstration significance for China's coordinated development of regional industries and even the world, which can be used for reference by more economic industrial zones in the future Development of relevant legal systems.

IV. Main problems of legal regulation on coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei

A. The coordinated legislation of Beijing Tianjin Hebei region needs to be improved

The coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei needs perfect legal guarantee. Therefore, it is one of the important problems to regulate the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei express industry by means of legislation. The current legislative system of our country is divided according to the administrative regions. Provinces, autonomous regions, municipalities directly under the central government and cities divided into districts have the local legislative power, while the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry spans three provinces and cities, which makes it impossible to make legal provisions for the entire industry of Beijing Tianjin Hebei region only for the departments with legislative power in this region, which makes the industrial cooperation of Beijing Tianjin Hebei region lack of legal provisions The legal basis of universal significance and authority. Therefore, in the face of the problems of how to implement the coordinated development of regional industry, how to carry out legal supervision, who will play the role of legal supervision, and how to make decisions in case of disputes, all of these have become obstacles to the coordinated development of regional industry, which makes the coordinated development of industry in a dilemma.

B. The mechanism of law enforcement cooperation needs to be improved

The law enforcement cooperation mechanism of the express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei needs to be improved. In the current law enforcement work, the supervision of the express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei mainly stays in the self supervision and self-management of each region, and has not yet built a unified law enforcement cooperation mechanism. Regional administrative barriers are the prominent obstacles that affect the law enforcement cooperation of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express delivery industry. In the formulation and implementation of the system, the three local governments tend to consider in their own administrative regions, rarely regarding the development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei region as the priority of planning and construction, and taking their own development and interests as the first consideration. The thinking pattern of "one acre and three parts of land" is widespread. In the absence of co management and co construction of industries in the region, the situation of non

cooperation in competition is relatively common, which adds great difficulty to the collaborative management and control of the three local governments whose own administrative power has a large gap. In Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei region, if the express industry can be linked by industrial links to form a relatively complete industrial chain, then the efficiency of the enterprise will be greatly improved, at the same time, it will help enterprises reduce production and operation costs, make resources and elements flow freely, and promote the better development of the whole express industry. However, in terms of the current situation of the three regions, the development of cross regional express industry chain is restricted by the administrative system. The three governments are independent and make industrial policies and plans only suitable for local development. And Beijing has a strong momentum of development, and seeks to form a complete industrial system within its own administrative region. The competition among the three real estate industries is common, but it is necessary to compare the regional advantages and promote the complementary development of industries. Different local governments have different ideas, motivations and value orientations. At the same time, because the actual situation of different regions is not the same, administrative conflicts will appear, which is the obstacle to strengthen regional industrial coordination. The establishment of cross regional and cross departmental law enforcement cooperation mechanism is conducive to strengthening the safety management of enterprises, standardizing the delivery process of goods, etc. Therefore, it is necessary to promote the law enforcement cooperation of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry, realize the joint administrative law enforcement of the three regions, timely and effectively crack down on illegal and criminal acts in enterprise operation, promote cross regional and cross departmental joint punishment, and guarantee the development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry.

C. Judicial cooperation system to be improved

Express delivery industry is a cross regional industry, so when some problems and cases arise, it often involves local courts to make decisions through cooperation. However, due to the gap in the process of legal construction in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and the constraints of local administrative barriers, it is difficult to deal with cross regional cases. Therefore, some scholars put forward suggestions to improve the judicial cooperation system of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei industries Degree, through a series of linkage and cooperation mechanisms to deal with cross regional cases in the coordinated development of industry, but the current grass-roots court for cooperation has a small coverage, and there are still cross regional cases that are not covered.

D. The construction of industry self-discipline mechanism needs to be improved

Industry self-discipline organization refers to the members in the same industry, with the purpose of promoting self-discipline and self-management of members and realizing common interests, playing the role of bridge and link between relevant departments and express industry. According to the relevant provisions of Article 60 of the postal law of the people's Republic of China, the express industry association has played an important role in strengthening self-discipline, promoting industry norms, safeguarding the legitimate rights and interests of the industry and safeguarding market order. As the self-

discipline organization of the express industry, the express industry association has been given the supervision responsibility of the express industry. At present, the express industry association includes China Express Association and local express Association. China Express association is approved by the State Council of the people's Republic of China and registered with the Ministry of civil affairs. At present, the relationship and cooperation between the three express associations are not deep enough, and the power division between the three express associations and the government supervision is not clear enough. There is a dual supervision system of the express industry association and rich supervision departments, which is bound to be not conducive to the supervision and management of the express enterprises.

E. The internal governance of express enterprises still needs to be strengthened

In terms of the current operation of express enterprises, many express outlets are closed due to poor operation. The most important reason is the widespread existence of the operation form of "add without alliance, connect without lock", which does not form a unified service standard and management standard, resulting in the loss of express outlets and the inability to continue operation. In this operation dilemma, many problems appear, such as personal information leakage, express lost, rough sorting and so on. Timeliness and security of express delivery

V. Measures to improve the legal regulation of coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei

A. Strengthen the coordination mechanism of legislative system design

The coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei needs the rule of law first. The construction of the coordinated legislation system in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei plays an important role in promoting the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and is conducive to improving the embarrassing situation caused by the factors such as the uncoordinated and conflicting legislation in the three regions. Since the implementation of the national strategy of coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, the three regions have carried out active exploration and practice in the aspect of coordinated legislation, but still need to improve the mechanism of Legislative Coordination.

1. Establish a complete legal system for regional coordination of express industry

In order to realize the coordinated management of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei industries in accordance with the law, it is a basic condition to establish a complete legal system of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei express industry coordination, so that all links of industrial development can truly be governed by the law. First of all, in the improvement and coordination of legislation, it is necessary to carry out collaborative legislation from the central level, from the overall and overall perspective, plan all aspects and elements of the whole industry as a whole, and improve the legal system on the basis of comprehensive consideration of the actual situation and legal basis of the three express industry, so as to ensure the fairness and stability of the development of the express industry. The cooperative legal system should keep pace with the times, regulate the application of law in the

coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and formulate corresponding legal interpretation when necessary. At the same time, the three governments of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei also need to work together, through holding joint meetings of the three governments or legislative coordination meetings to communicate the legislative situation of each region, establish a legislative discussion mechanism, and conduct research and formulation on detailed collaborative legislative issues.

2. Establish a unified regional legislative coordination organization for express industry

It is necessary to establish a unified and high-level legislative coordination organization to improve the legal regulation of the coordinated development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry. At present, the collaborative legislative work of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei is mainly carried out through communication and consultation in the form of symposiums. However, in the process of Legislative Coordination, there are many problems to be involved. At the same time, legislative research should be carried out in time. With the change of social development, laws that are not suitable for the collaborative development of current industries should be abolished, and imperfect laws should be revised and interpreted, repealed, established, modified Parallel interpretation. In this case, this kind of coordination legislation mode in the form of symposiums will not adapt to the problems of daily regional industrial coordination legislation for a long time, and will not be conducive to the long-term and in-depth development of the region. Therefore, in order to ensure the orderly operation of the collaborative legislation, it is necessary to set up an authoritative and specialized coordinating legislative body in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, which is responsible for the legislative issues related to the coordinated development of regional express industry, give full play to the leading role of legislation, thoroughly implement the principle of balance and coordination, and establish regional industrial cooperation.

3. Establish a legislative information sharing and exchange platform for express industry in three regions

It is very important to break the three administrative barriers, promote the high sharing of legislative resources, and exchange timely and accurate information. The establishment of the Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry legislation information exchange platform can let the three places know and share the legislation information in time, solve the problems quickly in the legislation work, strengthen the legislation coordination, save the legislation resources to the maximum extent, and improve the legislation efficiency. [1] at present, the reason for the slow progress of the collaborative legislation of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei is the lack of information exchange, which leads to the failure to reach an effective consensus on the distribution of interests and responsibilities among the three regions. All parties want to increase their own interests, reduce their own responsibilities, and have poor communication. The establishment of a legislative information exchange platform can make the communication and consultation mechanism more standardized and orderly, accelerate its integration process, create a favorable environment for collaborative legislation, and promote the communication and exchange of legislative achievements among the three regions. All the

new legislative achievements and experiences in the region should be put into the information sharing and exchange platform in time for the reference of the other two parties. The measures for coordination of legislative projects of the Beijing Tianjin Hebei People's Congress was adopted and implemented in 2017. According to Article 5 of the measures, the key projects of coordinated development should inform each other of their legislative planning and legislative achievements. In order to enhance the sharing of the achievements of rule of law, the three governments can upload their own industrial legislative suggestions and the implementation of laws on the legislative information platform at any time, so that the three parties can update the relevant legislative information in real time, understand the legislative dynamics of each other, and improve the efficiency of collaborative legislation.

B. Improve the law enforcement cooperation mechanism of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry

We need to thoroughly implement the relevant laws and regulations of the express industry, comprehensively promote the rule of law, and build a market management mechanism with unified government power and responsibility and strong supervision. Not only the express management departments in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei should strengthen the supervision and law enforcement of the express market, strictly deal with all kinds of illegal behaviors within their jurisdiction, and implement the supervision responsibility of express universal service. Law enforcement cooperation refers to the special rectification activities with legal basis organized by the government departments according to the provisions of the administrative compulsory law. Improving the law enforcement cooperation mechanism of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry is conducive to improving law enforcement supervision and strengthening the consciousness of enterprises to abide by laws and disciplines. Not only that, it will also improve the enthusiasm and initiative of the express enterprises in Beijing Tianjin Hebei to implement the main responsibility of safety production, but also help to train the law enforcement team, improve the law enforcement level and enforce the law discipline seriously.

Through organizing joint law enforcement actions, law enforcement information sharing, cross case investigation, discussion and exchange, the management departments of express service industry in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region can jointly build a law enforcement cooperation mechanism of multi-party joint governance, information resource sharing, and communication and cooperation. In the process of law enforcement and supervision, the relevant law enforcement departments in the three regions can break the regional restrictions, strengthen the exchange and cooperation of law enforcement in the express industry, and form a unified, efficient and convenient cooperation mechanism. At the same time, it is also necessary to establish an information platform for law enforcement cooperation between Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and timely communicate the work of all regions in the law enforcement of express industry through the information sharing mechanism, such as: law enforcement policies, normative documents, special law enforcement actions, existing problems and difficulties in law enforcement.

C. Improve the judicial cooperation system of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry

In July 2017, 15 Chinese and grass-roots courts in the Beijing Tianjin Hebei region jointly signed the judicial cooperation agreement of Chinese and grass-roots courts in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region. After that, the courts in the three agreements will cooperate in such links as filing, service, trial and execution in different places. Through the cross regional case identification, unified guidance and management mechanism, entrusted service mechanism, cross regional major, consultation mechanism, implementation of the linkage and cooperation mechanism to deal with all kinds of cases involved in the Beijing Tianjin Hebei region. The establishment of this judicial cooperation mechanism, actively implementing the integrated development strategy of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei from the implementation aspect, is conducive to further unifying the judgment standards of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and is a beneficial exploration in the judicial level of the coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei industries. However, at present, only a part of the middle and basic level courts in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region have signed the agreement. The judicial cooperation system does not cover the whole area of Beijing Tianjin Hebei region. We should implement the judicial cooperation agreement of middle and basic level courts in Beijing Tianjin Hebei region to every middle and basic level court in the region as soon as possible, so that when dealing with cross regional cases, judicial rights and interests can be guaranteed, more fair and just judgments can be obtained, and express delivery can be improved. The level of industry legalization and standardization.

D. Strengthen the self-discipline mechanism construction of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry

In order to maintain the coordinated rapid and stable development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express industry, in addition to the supervision of relevant government departments, it is also necessary to lack the supervision role of Express Industry Association in the process of enterprise operation, which is the most important supervision force besides the government and market supervision.

For the supervision of the express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, the regional express associations in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei should play a better role in the link between the government and enterprises, constantly enhance the self-discipline of the industry, safeguard the legitimate rights and interests of enterprises, and guide enterprises to improve the service quality. In the 13th five year plan for the development of express service in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei (hereinafter referred to as the 13th five year plan) Under the guidance of the three express associations, actively carry out exhibition conferences, academic research, surveys and various trainings related to the coordinated development of express industry, and establish information exchange channels. At the same time, it is also necessary to strengthen contacts and exchanges with express delivery associations in other regions and establish good communication and cooperation relations. In addition, the express industry association should also strengthen international cooperation and exchange, learn from the self-management and supervision experience of the association from developed countries such as Europe and the United

States. Clearly distinguish the management authority of express delivery Association and government supervision department, and completely eliminate the dual supervision system of Industry Association and government supervision department in industry supervision; in terms of the composition of Industry Association personnel, in addition to the representatives of government supervision department and member express enterprises, it is also necessary to increase the representatives of consumer rights organizations, so that the express delivery association can fully supervise the industry. We will play a complementary role in government regulation. We will encourage express associations to improve their work systems, formulate and strictly implement self-discipline regulations, strengthen the self-discipline mechanism of the express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and promote the coordinated development of the express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei.

E. Improve the internal governance mechanism of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express enterprises

The development of express industry can not only rely on the supervision and management of the government, so the market will not play its role in allocating resources and regulating economic activities, and lose its vitality. To improve the internal governance mechanism of Beijing Tianjin Hebei express enterprises, as the main body of express market, express enterprises should strengthen the internal governance of enterprises, establish perfect enterprise management system, strive to improve the service quality of enterprises, guide express enterprises to establish the concept of safety and development, improve the safety responsibility system of enterprises, and promote the sustainable and healthy development of express enterprises by strengthening the construction of standardization system. Exhibition. In the face of the problems of personal information leakage, express loss, rough sorting and so on, which infringe on the rights and interests of consumers, express enterprises should further improve the operation standards, service specifications and other aspects to improve the end service water.

VI. Conclusion

The coordinated development of Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei industries is a new historical task given to us by the new era. As a supporting industry of e-commerce, express industry is a modern leading industry to promote consumption upgrading, and has become an important force in the new momentum of economic development. The mature and stable market must be guaranteed by the rule of law. Therefore, under the guidance of the 13th five year plan, the legislative coordination agencies in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei should formulate a set of perfect and unified legal system as soon as possible according to the actual situation of the three regions, so as to realize the sustainable and healthy development of the express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei.

This paper analyzes the legal problems in the coordinated development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and puts forward the countermeasures to improve these problems, which are finally implemented into the improvement of Legislative Coordination Mechanism, the improvement of judicial and law enforcement cooperation system, the construction of self-discipline mechanism of

express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei, and the strengthening of internal governance mechanism of express enterprises, so as to ensure the healthy and orderly development of express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. Due to the limited research ability of the author, the research on the legal regulation of the coordinated development of the express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei still needs to be deepened. At present, the legal system of the coordinated development of the express industry in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei still has a lot of room for improvement. In order to solve the above problems, we need to go through continuous coordination and improvement. Based on the reality of the region, we need to formulate more scientific and reasonable legal regulation to promote the express industry Gradually mature and contribute to the prosperity and development of Beijing Tianjin Hebei Industrial integration.

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